

D3.5 - Toolkit for implementing tourism crowd detection solutions

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Executive Summary

This toolkit aims at facilitating the conception of tourism crowding monitoring applications, namely by including an online tutorial (video and textual contents) for building crowd detectors and installing its driving software (that will be made available on an open-source repository), as well as configuration and deployment instructions. This kind of application is especially relevant for tourism SMEs that organize events for large groups of tourists where they have to monitor the occupation of the space where it takes place, either to ensure better space management of attendees (e.g., to forward crowds to areas with lower occupancy), for security reasons (e.g., to avoid tampering with exposed objects in a museum space), health reasons (e.g., to avoid exceeding the maximum density of people allowed by health authorities in an event space to prevent contagion in times of pandemic), or simply because of workforce management considerations (e.g., to calculate the expected time for evacuating a concert arena to allow cleaning teams to proceed).

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>AP</i>	<i>Access Point</i>
<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>BIM</i>	<i>Building Information Model</i>
<i>CCTV</i>	<i>Close-Circuit TeleVision</i>
<i>DBMS</i>	<i>DataBase Management System</i>
<i>DC</i>	<i>Data Credit</i>
<i>DS</i>	<i>Device Status</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>GDPR</i>	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
<i>HNT</i>	<i>Helium Network Token</i>
<i>HTTP</i>	<i>HyperText Transfer Protocol</i>
<i>ICT</i>	<i>Information and Communications Technology</i>
<i>IE</i>	<i>Information Element</i>
<i>IEAA</i>	<i>Information Element Automatic Analyser</i>
<i>IEEE</i>	<i>Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers</i>
<i>IFTA</i>	<i>Inter-Frame Time Arrival</i>
<i>IoT</i>	<i>Internet of Things</i>
<i>IP</i>	<i>Internet Protocol</i>
<i>LoRaWAN</i>	<i>Long Range Wide Area Network</i>
<i>LTE</i>	<i>Long-Term Evolution</i>
<i>MAC</i>	<i>Media Access Control</i>
<i>MQTT</i>	<i>Message Queuing Telemetry Transport</i>
<i>NIC</i>	<i>Network Interface Controller</i>
<i>OS</i>	<i>Operating System</i>
<i>OUI</i>	<i>Organizational Unique Identifier</i>
<i>PNL</i>	<i>Preferred Network List</i>
<i>PoI</i>	<i>Point of Interest</i>
<i>PTZ</i>	<i>Pan-Tilt-Zoom</i>
<i>REST API</i>	<i>Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>RP-SMA</i>	<i>Reverse Polarity - SubMiniature version A</i>
<i>RSSI</i>	<i>Received Signal Strength Indicator</i>
<i>RV</i>	<i>Recreational Vehicle</i>
<i>SCB</i>	<i>Single Computer Board</i>
<i>SEQ</i>	<i>SEquence numbers</i>
<i>SHA</i>	<i>Secure Hash Algorithm</i>
<i>SIM</i>	<i>Subscriber Identity Module</i>
<i>SME</i>	<i>Small to Medium Enterprise</i>

SQL	<i>Structured Query Language</i>
SSID	<i>Service Set IDentifier</i>
SSL	<i>Semi-Supervised Learning</i>
STEP	<i>Sustainable Tourism Experience or Product</i>
STT	<i>Smart Tourism Tool</i>
STToolkit	<i>Toolkit for building STTs</i>
TCO	<i>Total Cost of Ownership</i>
UE	<i>User Equipment</i>
UI	<i>User Interface</i>
VPN	<i>Virtual Private Network</i>
VPS	<i>Virtual Private Server</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

Smart Tourism Tools (STTs) refer to the application of ICT for developing innovative tools and approaches to improve tourism. That improvement may express itself in diverse ways such as by enhancing tourism experiences, improving the efficiency of resource management at a micro and macro level, ensuring that benefits are well distributed and/or maximizing destination competitiveness with an emphasis on sustainable aspects. Summing up, STTs are a key element in improving the quality of tourism services provided by SMEs, boosting their competitiveness, strengthening their sustainability performance, and maintaining Europe's position as a leading tourist destination.

In the scope of Work Package 3, Task 3.3, hereinafter referred as WP3/T3.3, we aim at customizing, productizing, evaluating, and deploying STTs prototypes (products and or services) for facilitating the conception of tourism crowding monitoring applications, namely by including an online tutorial (video and textual contents) for building crowd detectors and installing its driving software (that will be made available on an open-source repository), as well as configuration and deployment instructions. This kind of application is especially relevant for tourism SMEs that organize events for large groups of tourists where they have to monitor the occupation of the space where it takes place, either to ensure better space management of attendees (e.g. to forward crowds to areas with lower occupancy), for security reasons (e.g. to avoid tampering with exposed objects in a museum space), health reasons (e.g. to avoid exceeding the maximum density of people allowed by health authorities in an event space to prevent contagion in times of pandemic), or simply because of workforce management considerations (e.g. to calculate the expected time for evacuating a concert arena to allow cleaning teams to proceed).

This deliverable proposes a toolkit (abbreviated as STToolkit) to scaffold the creation of the aforementioned STTs and is an instantiation of a previous RESETTING deliverable – “D3.3 - *Meta-manual for producing toolkits for STTs*”. Three types of stakeholders are considered, herein referred as **stakeholder roles**:

- **STToolkit Instantiator role** - SME member(s) (or subcontractor) in charge of instantiating / tailoring a given STToolkits to produce a desired Smart Tourism Tool (STTool);
- **STTool Operator role** - representing the SME member(s) in charge of operating the produced STTool (i.e. guaranteeing their availability to users and being able to troubleshoot and overcome failures in operation);
- **STTool User role** - representing the final users of the STTool, i.e. the tourists using it.

2. Deployment Scenarios

Deployment scenarios are business-driven and are inputs for both Technical Planning and Financial Planning. Each deployment scenario should include its location and range (e.g. from a few square meters indoor to wide outdoor areas). The latter may impose constraints (e.g. orography, urban fabric, the existence of power lines) that allow identifying other features, namely available communications facilities (e.g. Wi-Fi, LoRaWAN, mobile network). The availability of required technical skills in the SME team is also a critical scenario feature, since their absence may hamper deployment and/or cause cost surplus due to required subcontracting.

We now introduce a set of deployment scenarios for this STToolkit.

2.1. Outdoor Continuously Intensive Scenario

Examples of this scenario include the visitation of historical open-air sites, public parks, as well as areas of beautiful landscapes or monuments. Overtourism can have severe negative impacts on beautiful natural landscapes and their habitats. Such impacts include habitat fragmentation or destruction and wildlife disturbance leading to resource depletion, altered ecosystems, and therefore wildlife population declines. Other side effects include waste pollution, water scarcity, and a carbon footprint increase. On the other hand, if the tourists' attraction is due to the historical value of the destination itself, then overtourism can disrupt the traditional lifestyles and cultures of local communities. Increased commercialization and the influx of outsiders can erode indigenous practices and social structures. What was once pristine and authentic can become commercialized and artificial, therefore degrading the visiting experience.

Data collected by crowding sensors in overcrowded tourism destinations can be a valuable resource for tourism stakeholders, including tourists themselves, to mitigate the consequences of overtourism. That data can be used to provide tourists with real-time recommendations, redirecting them to less crowded areas, by informing them what and when to visit, thereby reducing the impact on critical spots. Tourism stakeholders can allocate resources such as local police and urban

cleaning services to mitigate the negative impacts of crowding, protecting both tourists (e.g. against pickpocketing) and natural or cultural resources. Alerts can also warn local authorities when predefined carrying capacity limits are exceeded so that they can temporarily restrict access until crowds thin out to manageable levels. Local communities can also access data to understand visitor patterns and plan events or services that align with tourism trends. This can enhance the economic benefits of tourism while minimizing disruption to traditional lifestyles. Last, but not the least, Crowding data can help conservation organizations identify areas that are most affected by overcrowding. This information can guide conservation and restoration efforts in high-impact areas.

2.2. Indoor Continuously Intensive Scenario

This scenario relates to the visitation of indoor sites such as museums or palaces. The two main problems in managing highly sought-after destinations with these characteristics are admissions control and internal management of occupancy and flow between the various rooms. Regarding the former, crowding sensor data can help optimize reservation slots, ensuring a steady flow of visitors throughout the day and preventing overcrowding during peak hours. Crowding data can also inform dynamic pricing models. Higher entry fees during peak times can incentivize visitors to choose less crowded times, helping to distribute the flow of tourists more evenly.

As for managing the visiting flow, more attractive rooms, containing masterpieces or high-valued historical traces, tend to be congested. Besides security issues, those crowded rooms become stressful for visitors, mainly those not tall (like children), affected by breathing conditions, or with mobility impairments.

Sensors measuring the occupancy of each room in these indoor destinations can play a significant role in mitigating the previous issues. This real-time information can help staff and security personnel monitor and manage visitors' density effectively. For instance, if a room is nearing its carrying capacity, visitors can be directed to other rooms or asked to wait a few moments until the room becomes less crowded. Another option is to have digital displays at room entrances or in a dedicated app, showing real-time occupancy levels allowing visitors to make informed decisions about which rooms to visit, helping them avoid waiting times. Another possible

mitigation action is to have an app or information kiosk that allows visitors to indicate which rooms or topics (in the case of a museum) they do not want to miss, that produces a recommended route that meets the formulated requirements, but which optimizes the route of your visit, reducing waiting times due to overcrowded rooms. In the event of an emergency or security threat, sensors can also help identify the location of visitors within the building, enabling a faster and more organized evacuation or response.

2.3. Outdoor Time-limited Intensive Scenario

Several tourism-intensive activities span a limited time frame, ranging from a few weeks (e.g., a campsite or an RV park¹) to a few days (e.g., a pop/rock festival), or even only a few hours (e.g., a fireworks or video mapping show).

Campsites and RV (Recreational Vehicle) parks usually have shared facilities such as toilets, sinks, showers, picnic areas with campfire rings or pits, playgrounds, convenience stores, and laundry facilities. Such amenities are usually under intensive usage in peak periods when the park is full. Waiting queues then appear, causing stress among campers, sometimes leading to aggressive arguments.

Crowding sensors placed near those critical shared facilities can be used to provide (e.g. through a dedicated mobile app) real-time information on estimated wait times for facilities or, using predictive analytics techniques, to recommend off-peak usage to campers, therefore helping campers make informed decisions, encouraging them to use amenities during quieter times. Park management can also allocate staff to critical facilities based on real-time data. For example, if the crowding sensor indicates a long restroom queue, additional restroom cleaning staff can be dispatched to ensure cleanliness and efficiency. Combined with users' feedback, long-term data collected by crowding sensors can inform decisions about expanding shared facilities or adding new ones for the next high season.

¹ Although many campsites are open all year round, they are only crowded a few weeks a year, usually in July/August in the case of Europe.

More short-term intensively crowded scenarios such as a pop/rock festival, fireworks, or a video mapping show, which require thorough planning for allocating resources such as paramedics, police officers, urban cleaning teams, and their equipment (ambulances, patrol cars, garbage collection trucks, and other urban cleaning vehicles). By harnessing the power of crowding sensors near the entries/exits and data analytics, event organizers and/or local authorities can enhance crowd management, improve public safety (by facilitating emergency response), and optimize resource allocation (allocation and release) during short-term intensively crowded scenarios, ensuring a safer and more enjoyable experience for event attendees while efficiently utilizing essential resources. For instance, real-time data can be shared with event attendees through mobile apps or displays, informing them about crowd conditions and safety measures. This helps attendees make informed decisions and reduces anxiety. Historical data can also be analyzed to evaluate resource allocation effectiveness and identify areas for improvement in future events.

2.4. Sparse Yet Critical Scenario

This scenario covers situations where, although human visitation may be light, if not carefully controlled it may endanger the environment due to its fragility. Such is the case of wildlife sanctuaries. Wildlife observation in their original habitat is a compelling component of eco-tourism because it combines education, conservation, economic development, and personal enrichment while promoting responsible and sustainable tourism practices. It allows tourists to connect with nature, fostering a deeper appreciation for the environment and the need to protect it for future generations. The most common wildlife observation found in Europe is bird-watching where thousands of such spots exist all over Europe and the Mediterranean ².

Birds should be allowed uninterrupted feeding or nesting. When threatened by the sight of human presence, they will tend to flee. To allow close observation, camouflaged shelters are built. Even so, the noise caused by a group of visitors in a shelter will also betray the human presence, disrupting the natural behaviors of birds intended to be observed, which ultimately will fly away. Crowd sensors installed in each shelter in the natural park for bird watching can play a crucial role in managing group visits and minimizing disturbances to birdlife. Those sensors can be utilized for occupancy monitoring, noise level monitoring, visitor

² <https://www.birdingplaces.eu/>

guidance on responsible behavior during briefing meetings, real-time alerts (to park rangers or staff responsible for visitor management), post-mortem visitor behavior analysis, dynamic scheduling of group visits, and other data-driven decision-making strategies to protect wildlife.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the suggested usage scenarios for this STToolkit.

Table 1 – Deployment Scenarios Characterization

Scenario Features	Outdoor Continuously Intensive	Indoor Continuously Intensive	Outdoor Time-limited Intensive	Sparse Yet Critical
Location	Outdoor	Indoor	Outdoor	Outdoor
Visitation	Intensive throughout all year round	Intensive visitation all year round	Intensive within a given time frame	Sparse (low intensity) occupancy, but critical to wildlife
Examples	Historical open-air sites, public parks, beautiful landscape or monumental areas	Museums, palaces	Campsites, RV parks, pop/rock festivals, fireworks or video mapping shows	Bird watching spaces, natural parks
Range	< 1Km	< 100m	< 300m	Few Kms
Communication facilities	LoRaWan or WiFi	WiFi or Bluetooth	WiFi	LoRaWan or WiFi

3. Toolkit Classification

This section classifies this toolkit according to the STT taxonomy proposed in the RESETTING deliverable “D3.3 - Meta-manual for producing toolkits for STTs”. This same taxonomy will be used to classify the STTs that will populate the European Observatory on Smart Tourism Tools being developed in the context of Task 3.2 of Work Package 3.

The proposed taxonomy has several aspects, described in the following subsections.

3.1. Action Domain and Tool Type

According to the proposed taxonomy, the action domains and corresponding STT types we could identify for this STTool are those detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 – Classification of Action Domain and Tool Type

ACTION DOMAIN	STT TYPE	DESCRIPTION
(Part of) the touristic offer	Partial digital experience	STT enables and/or enriches the tourist experience in the real world with additional and registered digital content (e.g., augmented reality tours).
	Building block	Scaffolding tools that support the enrichment of the tourist experience (e.g., audio or video content creation).
Management & Operations	Operation of tourism products	STT assists in the operation of touristic offerings (e.g., crowd management tools).
	Maintenance/evolution of tourism products	STT helps in the evaluation and decision-making regarding the existing touristic offer (e.g., data analytics tools).

3.2. Technical Characterization

The technologies required to instantiate this STT are:

- Data Analytics and Visualization
- Edge computers
- Software installation/configuration
- Bluetooth and Wi-Fi connectivity
- Geographical Information Systems
- Databases (e.g. SQL, NoSQL, Timeseries).

3.3. Required Skills

The STTools based on our toolkit include both hardware and software that must be installed and configured/tuned at a given location before being put into operation. Then, when the system is in operation with final users, we should guarantee that it keeps providing its service smoothly without interruptions or service degradation. Therefore, we considered separately the required skills for hardware and software in those two phases: installation and maintenance, resulting in four different categories: skills required for hardware installation, skills required for software installation, skills required for hardware maintenance, and skills required for software maintenance.

Followingly we briefly characterize each of the former four categories and then gauge their required level of skills using a semantic differential scale in Figure 1, where two bipolar adjectives are used at the endpoints: generalist and specialist. Generalist skills are those based on common sense or due to exposure to technologies used in day-to-day life, like using a mobile phone and installing apps on it. Specialized skills are those that require specific technical training (formal or professional) and/or effective hands-on in-depth experience.

3.3.1. On installation

- Hardware: Case assembly, solar panels mounting, electrical cabling, etc.
- Software: Follow instructions on how to set up the control software for the sensors and website cloud server. Customize the installation according to the sensors' location conditions. Website configuration and customization.

3.3.2. During maintenance

- Hardware: Network and electrical troubleshooting, camera adjusting, etc.
- Software: Adjustments to the website customization.

Figure 1 - Required skills for hardware and software installation and maintenance

3.4. Sustainability Focus

This aspect deals with the concern on sustainability matters considered during STT development. We will use here the same sustainability indicators used for STEPs (Sustainable Tourism Experiences and Products) to be developed in the scope of Task 3.6 (Sustainable B2B Marketplace). These indicators are defined along with 3 dimensions:

- **Environmental sustainability.** Environmental performance evaluation considering:
 - Land use;
 - Energy use;
 - Resource extraction;
 - Water use;
 - Pollution of water and soil;
 - GreenHouse gas emissions;
 - Other air pollutant emissions.

- **Social sustainability.** Social performance evaluation mainly focused on understanding:
 - Labor relations/conditions;
 - Relations with the community;
 - Customer relations;
 - Supplier control and fair trade policy;
 - "Edutainment" value.

- **Destination sustainability.** Evaluation of the quality, sensibility, and sustainability of the destination on a regional scale. Qualification of the territory and understanding of the local impact of your STT considering:
 - Environmental quality (resource use, pollution levels, natural status);
 - Socio-cultural authenticity;
 - Level of heritage protection (natural, socio-cultural, and/or built).

The indicator for each of the latter is rated on a **5-point Likert scale** (e.g. Extremely Effective - 5, Very Effective - 4, Moderately Effective - 3, Slightly Effective - 2, Not at all Effective - 1), in response to these questions **for STT's final users (tourists)**, and combined in a Kiviat Diagram (aka Radar Chart), for each of the planned deployment scenarios (Figures 2 through 5), to allow a more concise view and comparability of the sustainability focus provided by the STT.

Figure 2 - Outdoor Continuously Intensive scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 3 - Indoor Continuously Intensive scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 4 - Outdoor Time-limited Intensive scenario sustainability indicators

Figure 5 - Sparse Yet Critical scenario sustainability indicators

3.5. Accessibility Focus

This aspect deals with the concern on accessibility matters considered during STT development. In other words, we aim to evaluate if people with disabilities will benefit by using or operating the STT. We will consider two populations: one of final users (i.e., tourists) and another of STT operators, i.e. those who install the STT and ensure its operation/availability. We consider 4 disability/impairment dimensions: vision, hearing, mobility, and cognition.

The indicator for each of the latter will be rated on a **5-point Likert scale** (e.g. Extremely Effective - 5, Very Effective - 4, Moderately Effective - 3, Slightly Effective - 2, Not at all Effective - 1), in response to these questions **for STT's final users (tourists) and STT operators (installation and operation)**:

- How effective is it to allow users with vision disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?
- How effective is it to allow users with hearing disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?
- How effective is it to allow users with mobility disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?
- How effective is it to allow users with cognitive disabilities to use it for the intended purpose?

To allow a more concise view and comparability of the accessibility focus provided by the STT, a double Kiviatt Diagram (aka Radar Chart) is used in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - Tourists and operators accessibility indicators

4. STT System Description

This section describes system components that integrate the STToolkits, including both hardware (e.g. sensors) and software (e.g. cloud-based) components.

4.1. System Architecture

The architecture of each STToolkit is described in the UML Component Diagram presented in the image below. The Component Diagram describes the organization and wiring of STT components. The latter are conceptual stand-alone design elements that provide or require interfaces to interact with other constructs (aka artifacts) in the STT.

The components filled in yellow are re-used open-source components, while the components filled in blue are customized components purposely created for the STToolkit.

Figure 7 - STToolkit architecture

A flexible architecture has been designed, where sensors collect the crowding information in its vicinity and periodically report the crowding levels to a cloud server. The latter also has other components for making downlink communication transparent and providing uplink services for rendering the information and creation of notification policies.

The STToolkit architecture is divided into three main parts:

- **Crowding Data Collection** - This part regards the STToolkit's sensors. It includes both hardware and software components for the crowding data collection in their vicinity and for the data upload to the cloud server.
- **Communication & Services** - This part regards the communication and services of the STToolkit. It includes the components for the data upload of the crowding levels, the data ingestion and storage from sensors on the cloud server, as well as the crowding data renderization for further visualization.
- **Visualization & Notification** - This regards the visualization and notification of the STToolkit. It includes the components for end users to visualize the crowding data gathered by the multiple sensors and the creation of notification policies to alert operators of events, such as overcrowding situations.

4.1.1. Crowding Data Collection

The *CrowdingSensor* represents the STToolkit's sensors. Each *CrowdingSensor* has firmware that controls the hardware used to detect mobile devices in each wireless technology, namely, the *WiFiFirmware* for the detection in Wi-Fi technology, and *BluetoothFirmware* for Bluetooth technology. The detection of mobile devices is performed by the *WiFiCrowdingSensor* and the *BluetoothCrowdingSensor* for each technology, which, from these, the *WiFiCrowdingDetector* and the *BluetoothCrowdingDetector*, inherit its properties. These last two are components purposely customized for passively capturing mobile devices' trace elements in each wireless technology and inserting the collected data into the *DetectionsDB*, the anonymized sensor's local database. The *DetectionsDB* stores all collected data by the sensor.

The *DetectionsDB* is created due to the existence of a DataBase Management System (*DBMS*), responsible for the data management of the sensor. The *DBMS* also provides an interface for two other custom-made components, the *DataRetentionManager*, responsible for only retaining the useful information for device counting by cleaning outdated and unnecessary data from the *DetectionsDB*, and the *DetectionEngine*, responsible for counting the number of devices by

analyzing the information contained in the *DetectionsDB* and periodically uploading the crowding levels to the *CrowdingServer*, the STToolkit's cloud server.

The sensors can perform only Wi-Fi or Bluetooth detection, or both at the same time, where switching between the technologies used for detection should be quick and simple.

4.1.2. *Communication & Services*

A flexible deployment regarding several uplink technologies has been considered for the STToolkit architecture. The crowding levels can be uploaded to the *CrowdingServer* using two communication protocols: Wi-Fi or LoRaWAN.

The most straightforward option to choose from is the data upload via Wi-Fi. If Wi-Fi coverage is available at the installation location of the sensors, data can be directly uploaded to the cloud server, being received at the *MessageServer* component, a [Mosquitto MQTT Broker](#), via MQTT protocol, a lightweight method of carrying out messaging widely used for IoT applications. This option can be applied straightforwardly in indoor tourism scenarios, for instance, in museums or monasteries, which generally provide Wi-Fi network coverage to visitors.

In tourism outdoor scenarios, such as public parks or city squares, where overtourism situations can also arise, Wi-Fi coverage may not be available. As so, to mitigate the network limitations at the installation location, the STToolkit also offers the option for uploading data via the LoRaWAN protocol, a low-cost alternative that provides scalability and is feasible for our application since sensors only communicate a small amount of data, i.e., the number of detected devices. For this, sensors must be equipped with a dedicated LoRa board and corresponding antenna, to communicate the crowding information to a LoRaWAN gateway, presented as the *ProxyServer* component, that, in turn, will route the information to the *MessageServer* also via MQTT protocol.

Regarding LoRa coverage, the crowdsourced [Helium](#) network was the LoRa network chosen for uploading data. Helium is one of the fastest growing IoT networks and provides a large and extensive coverage in many European countries, such as those involved in the RESETTING project. Therefore, an SME can choose from three options to upload data to the *CrowdingServer*:

- Wi-Fi on site (when available);
- Helium with third-party LoRaWAN service provider (e.g., [Helium-IoT](#));
- Helium with private LoRaWAN server;

As so, from all the options available, an SME must choose the option that best fits their needs and requirements for the STToolkit.

Furthermore, in areas with low or no Wi-Fi or LoRaWAN coverage, such as a remote camping site or a rural tourism facility, it is also possible to acquire equipment to provide such coverage, such as a Wi-Fi mesh system, that will allow the expansion of the Wi-Fi network coverage, and also Helium hotspots, for grating Helium network coverage at the installation location of the sensor.

The crowding measurements from sensors are received on the *CrowdingServer*, the STToolkit's cloud server, on the *Message Server* component via MQTT protocol, either via Wi-Fi or LoRaWAN protocols. This ensures transparency as all messages are received at the same point, regardless of the communication protocol used for uploading the crowding information.

The messages received in the *MessageServer* are then collected by the *CrowdingCollector*, a [Telegraf](#) agent, that pushes them to the *CrowdingDB*. The *CrowdingDB* is an [InfluxDB](#) database and is responsible for the data ingestion and storage of all crowding measurements sent by all sensors of the STToolkit. It can be viewed as the main database of the system. The *CrowdingDB* will then store the entire information collected from all sensors and also provide support for several data visualization platforms to render the crowding information.

4.1.3. Visualization & Notification

The *CrowdingServer* also has several components for uplink services that can be used by users to understand the crowding levels in the areas where each sensor is deployed in a clear and simple perspective. The crowding services can provide:

- Rendering of temporal information;
- Rendering of geographical information;
- Notification policies (e.g., notifying operators when a crowding threshold is reached);
- Raw data for custom-made integrations (e.g., spatial visualization using avatars in a Building Information Model (BIM)).

The *VisualizationPlatform* component is responsible for the data visualization of the STToolkit. The latter connects directly to the *CrowdingDB* and rapidly queries the stored data from the database, which is then further rendered and visualized in dashboards. Data can be used to render temporal information, with graphs to perceive people's concentration and flows during specified periods

throughout the day, highly populated events and their duration, and for comparing crowding between locations at any particular time or time range. In addition, data can also be used for spatial and geographical renderization, with maps that allow users to understand how people are distributed through the several locations where the sensors are deployed. The data visualization platform chosen for the STToolkit was [Grafana](#), and is related to the *VisualizationPlatform* component. For facilitating its installation and configuration, the STToolkit will provide pre-configured Grafana dashboards that operators can import for a quick and straightforward data visualization setup with all the previously mentioned features.

The *VisualizationPlatform* also has the *AlertingEngine* component, which provides the creation of notification policies for notifying users of events, such as when a crowding threshold is reached, or to simply advise on waiting times at a particular time of the day.

Then, STToolkit's operators and end users can visualize the crowding data by simply using a web browser to access Grafana on the cloud server, gaining access to the crowding visualization dashboards to visualize the crowding data from sensors.

Furthermore, the raw crowding data can also be used for third-party integrations. For this, other applications can directly connect to the *CrowdingDB* for querying the raw crowding data from the database, which can further be used for custom-made integrations, for instance, using the crowding data with walking avatars on top of a BIM to achieve a more realistic perception of space occupancy. The *Third-PartyIntegration* component represents those integrations that can be created by directly gathering the crowding data from the *CrowdingDB*.

4.2. Bill of Materials

This bill of materials describes the several choice/trade-off criteria when equivalent options are expected to be found, with a description of different deployment configurations of runtime solutions.

4.2.1. Crowd Sensors

This section describes the bill of materials of the STToolkit's crowd sensors. It includes the hardware part list, with several alternatives for computing elements, communication, and casing.

Table 4 presents the hardware available for the STToolkit's sensors, with several options for some of its functions.

Computing Resources:

For the sensor processing unit, there are two options available: the Raspberry Pi 3 or the Raspberry Pi 4 models. Although slightly more expensive, the Raspberry Pi 4 models have greater performances compared to its predecessor Raspberry Pi 3. As so, we recommend choosing the Raspberry Pi 4 for the sensor's processing unit. Furthermore, 1 GB RAM is the minimum requirement.

For sensor storage, there are plenty of microSD cards that can be acquired for the SBCs. The question remains on what are the best-performing microSD cards. Generally, micro-SD cards with high read/write speeds are the best performing and should have a V10 speed class. SanDisk is a well-known and popular manufacturer when it comes to memory cards, and so we recommend purchasing micro-SD cards from this manufacturer, although micro-SD cards from any other manufacturer are also valid for the sensors. In particular, the SanDisk Extreme Pro, Extreme, and High Endurance micro-SD are the best-performing memory cards from this manufacturer. For capacity, we recommend a micro-SD card with a minimum of 32GB, however, higher capacities can always be provided.

The power supply needs to be acquired according to the Raspberry Pi model chosen for the sensor.

Device Detection:

For Wi-Fi detection, the Alfa Network AWUS036ACH, the Alfa Network AWUS036ACM, and the Alfa Network AWUS036AC Wi-Fi network cards are available for the sensors. Each of these cards comes already with two omnidirectional antennas with 5 dBi gain that can be used for detecting devices in all directions.

For Bluetooth detection, the Ubertooth-One is available for the STToolkit. In fact, this is the most expensive hardware component of the sensor. Nevertheless, keep in mind that this component is only needed for the Bluetooth detection of devices. If an SME only intends to have Wi-Fi detection, there is no need to acquire this equipment.

Antennas:

The Alfa Network AOA-2458-79AM omnidirectional antenna can be used for communication purposes. It is a high-gain omnidirectional antenna that can be used for grating a good communication range.

In some cases, it could be necessary to detect devices only in specific directions. The Alfa Network APA-M25 directional antenna can be used for this purpose. For this, the omnidirectional antennas can be replaced by this antenna, and the sensor will only detect devices in the direction of the directional antenna.

Upload:

The hardware described in this section can be used when there is no or low Wi-Fi coverage at the installation location of sensors, which need to rely on other communication protocols to upload the crowding data.

In the case of LoRaWAN upload, the sensor needs to be equipped with a Raspberry Pi IoT LoRa PHAT board for uploading the crowding data. The latter can be connected to the Alfa Network AOA-2458-79AM omnidirectional antenna for greater range.

In case LoRaWAN coverage is also not provided, there is also the option for implementing a Wi-Fi mesh system. The latter allows the expansion of Wi-Fi network coverage to the deployment location of the sensor. As the network card of the Raspberry Pi does not support the 802.11s communication protocol for implementing Wi-Fi mesh, an external Wi-Fi dongle needs to be acquired for that purpose. We recommend the TP-Link TL-WN722N dongle for implementing Wi-Fi mesh on the Raspberry Pi. This dongle can also be connected to the Alfa Network AOA-2458-79AM omnidirectional antenna for greater range.

Casing:

Two sensor case versions were designed for the STToolkit sensors: a larger version with no exposed antennas, and a smaller version with exposed antennas. The two versions have small dimensions, are waterproofed, and were designed to fit all the hardware of the crowd sensors. The two sensor case versions and their dimensions are presented below.

The sensor cases can be manufactured using 3D printing or a laser cutting machine. The files used to build them are available in the [RESETTING GitHub repository](#), along with some images of the cases. These cases can be fabricated at [Vitruvius Fablab - Iscte](#), an architecture lab at Iscte, which you can also contact to manufacture your sensor cases.

Figure 8 - Crowd Sensor Cases. Larger version with no exposed antennas (top) and smaller version with exposed antennas (down).

Table 3 – Sensor cases dimensions

Sensor Case	Dimensions		
	Width	Length	Depth
Larger version	24 cm	13,5 cm	6 cm
Smaller version	16,5 cm	12,4 cm	5,1 cm

The images below show examples of the deployment of the crowd sensors in real scenarios.

Figure 9 - Crowd sensors deployed in real scenarios

Table 4 – Crowd Sensors Bill of Materials

HARDWARE	FUNCTION	EQUIPMENT	UNIT COST
COMPUTING RESOURCES	PROCESSING	Raspberry Pi 4 4GB RAM	63.96€
		Raspberry Pi 3 1GB RAM	39.93 €
	STORAGE	SanDisk 32GB microSDXC High Extreme Pro	13.80 €
		SanDisk 32GB microSDXC Extreme	12.19 €
		SanDisk 32GB microSDXC High Endurance	11.21 €
	POWER SUPPLY	Raspberry Pi 4 USB-C Power Supply	8.75 €
		Raspberry Pi 3 Micro-USB Power Supply	8.65 €
DEVICE DETECTION	WI-FI DETECTION	Alfa Network AWUS036ACH	57.95 €
		Alfa Network AWUS036ACM	38.95 €
		Alfa Network AWUS036AC	36.95 €
	BLUETOOTH DETECTION	Ubertooth-One	152.78 €
ANTENNAS	OMNI-DIRECTIONAL ANTENNA	Alfa Network AOA-2458-79AM	18.95 €
	DIRECTIONAL ANTENNA	Alfa Network APA-M25	17.75 €
UPLOAD ³	LORAWAN UPLOAD	Raspberry Pi IoT LoRa pHAT	29.23 €
	WI-FI MESH UPLOAD	TP-Link TL-WN722N	11.17 €
CASING	LARGER VERSION	Sensor Larger Case	90.00 €
	SMALLER VERSION	Sensor Smaller Case	50.00 €

Therefore, the minimum recommended sensor unit cost, in a typical location with Wi-Fi coverage, considering the Raspberry Pi 4 model for the sensor’s processing unit, without Bluetooth detection and LoRaWAN upload, and using the larger sensor case version to conceal all hardware is 210.87€.

4.2.2. Cloud Server

The STToolkit’s cloud server also has some costs associated. The cloud server is hosted by a VPS, providing all resources for this component. Usually, suppliers charge monthly fees for hosting VPS. Table 5 shows the hosting costs of two VPS configurations for different providers.

³Hardware options in case of no or low Wi-Fi coverage at the installation location of the sensor.

Table 5 – VPS hosting costs for different VPS Providers

VPS Provider	Cloud Server Resources	Hosting Cost (without taxes)	
		Month	Year
DreamHost	1 CPU + 2 GB RAM	11,00 €	132,00 €
	4 CPU + 8 GB RAM	45,00 €	540,00 €
Contabo	1 CPU + 2 GB RAM	-	-
	4 CPU + 8 GB RAM	6,00 €	72,00 €
Kamatera	1 CPU + 2 GB RAM	6,00 €	72,00 €
	4 CPU + 8 GB RAM	37,00€	444,00 €

4.3. Source Code

All source code developed in the RESETTING project in the context of each STToolkit is available on the following GitHub site: <https://github.com/resetting-eu/crowdingSTToolkit>. It is well-documented so that html pages can be generated out of it with a documentation generator.

5. Financial Planning

5.1. Total Cost of Ownership Dimensions

The crowding STToolkit provides guidelines for costs incurred in its instantiation. These guidelines take into account several deployment scenarios and, for each of them, a characterization of which direct and indirect cost dimensions should be considered, to allow stakeholders to produce a financial estimate for their products or services, which is often dubbed **Total Cost of Ownership (TCO)**. Several dimensions are referred to in the literature for the TCO ⁴, such as those represented in Figure 8.

*Figure 10 – Breakdown of TCO into its dimensions
(found in multiple sites; original source could not be identified)*

We aggregated the previous dimensions in just three, as represented in Table 6 since the prolific dimensions in Figure 8 are only worth considering for large investments, not for a STTool aimed at being exploited by a tourism SME, whose main conception investment – the “intelligence” provided by its software – is free (open-source), due to the research being developed in the scope of the RESETTING project.

⁴- See, for instance, “*Total Cost of Ownership*”, 3rd edition, by Gerardus Blokdyk, January 2022, 5STARCOoks, ISBN-13: 978-0655312215

Table 6 – STTool TCO Dimensions

TCO DIMENSION	DESCRIPTION
Setup	Costs incurred in buying (see “Bill of Materials” section) and assembling the components of the STTool and making it available to final users (the tourists).
Operation	Costs incurred in guaranteeing STTool’s smooth operation (high availability), including user reporting mechanisms, fixing detected bugs, and monitoring the provided service through adequate dashboarding and/or other data analytics approaches to identify improvement opportunities and deploy the corresponding service upgrades. This may include hosting and communication fees.
Training	Costs incurred in training SME members in charge of setting up and operating the STTool.

5.2. Deployment Scenarios Cost Estimation

The Crowding STToolkit provides guidelines to allow SMEs to assess TCO’s dimensions for the chosen scenarios represented in Table 7.

Table 7 – TCO Cost per Dimension (for 10 locations with sensors)

TCO Dimension (€/month)	Outdoor Continuously Intensive	Indoor Continuously Intensive	Outdoor Time-limited Intensive	Sparse Yet Critical
Setup (min)	259.65 €	363.65 €	240.99 €	259.05 €
Operation (min)	6 €	6 €	6 €	6 €
Training	0 €	0 €	0 €	0 €
TCO (€/month)	2596.50 €	3636.50 €	2409.90 €	2590.50 €

The “Setup” regards the minimum costs incurred in buying the sensor hardware for each scenario. The “Operation” regards the minimum monthly cost for hosting the VPS for the STTool. The “Training” dimension has no costs associated.

MANUALS

Table 8 summarizes the manuals created in the scope of this STToolkit, along with the corresponding target roles. These manuals are complemented with video tutorials available on the [RESETTING YouTube channel](#) and textual descriptions (e.g. README files) in the [RESETTING GitHub repository](#).

Table 8 – TCO Cost per Dimension (for 10 locations with sensors)

Name	Target Role	Description
Cloud Server Installation Manual	STToolkit Instantiator	Guidelines for installation and integration of the cloud server required for a STT based on this STToolkit
Crowd Sensors Installation Manual	STToolkit Instantiator	Guidelines for installation and integration of the crowd sensors required for a STT based on this STToolkit
Operation Manual	STToolkit Operator	Guidelines for operation and troubleshooting of a STT based on this STToolkit
End User's Manual	STToolkit User	Illustrates the user's experience for a STT based on this STToolkit

6. Cloud Server Installation Manual

This manual includes the step-by-step detailed tutorial for the installation and configuration of the Cloud Server of the STToolkit, and the software that should live on it.

Follow the steps below in the correct order to install and configure the STToolkit's Cloud Server. The steps for chapters 1 and 2 are also available as a video tutorial on the [RESETTING Youtube channel](#). The steps for chapters 3 and 4 are also available as a video tutorial on the [RESETTING Youtube channel](#).

6.1. Cloud Server Acquisition

These steps regard the acquisition of a Virtual Private Server (VPS) for hosting the STToolkit's Cloud Server. The steps reproduce the acquisition of a VPS from [Contabo](#), however, any other VPS provider is valid for the STToolkit.

- 1) Create a user account on [Contabo](#).
- 2) Once logged in, on the 'New Order' yellow panel, select 'VPS'.

Several VPS configurations should appear, with different cloud resources and monthly charges.

3) Select a VPS configuration.

Note: We recommend choosing a VPS with at least **4 CPUs** and **4 GB RAM**. In the case of Contabo, the VPS configuration that fits these recommended requirements is a VPS with **4 CPUs** and **8 GB RAM**.

4) Configure the VPS.

Insert the following server configurations:

- i) Term length: (as desired by you)
- ii) Region: European Union (Germany)
- iii) Storage Type: 200 GB SSD or 400 GB SSD
- iv) Image: Ubuntu 22.04
- v) Login & password for your server:
 - a. Username: root
 - b. Password: (as desired by you)

Note: Please do not forget this password! It will be later necessary to remotely access the VPS.

- vi) Networking:
 - a. Private Networking: No Private Networking
 - b. IPv4: 1 IP Address
- vii) Add-ons: None

5) Order the VPS.

6) You should receive an email from Contabo confirming your payment and requiring some data verification before setting up the server. Please respond to this e-mail with the required information, as only after this verification procedure the server will be ready for use.

Note: If you made this step on a weekend, the verification should only be proceeded on the next working day. If so, please be patient and wait for the next working day.

7) After the data verification process from Contabo, you should receive an e-mail with your login data, with the server public IP address and other useful information of the server, similar to the one shown below.

Dear **Thomas**,

With this e-mail we would like to welcome you once again at Contabo!
Your order has been processed successfully. You can find all login data and details necessary to manage your order below.

If you just started using our services, we recommend you check our [First Steps with Contabo](#) tutorial.

Customer ID 123267118 (Order ID 123267144)

Please quote your customer ID in all communications with us, whether on the telephone or by e-mail. This ensures the fastest processing of your requests.

Your VPS

IP address	server type	Location	VNC IP and port	VNC password	user name	password
193.70.244.102	VPS 2 (20GB)	Nuremberg, DEU	193.70.244.102:5901	root@193.70.244.102	root	as chosen by you during order process

The Cloud Server is now available for the STToolkit. Let's try to remotely access it via SSH.

8) Open a command line terminal.

Windows:

Open the **Start menu** or press the **Windows** key, and type **cmd**. Press Enter.

MacOS:

Go to **Applications > Utilities** and double-click on **Terminal**.

9) Remotely access the Cloud Server via SSH using the root user credentials.

```
$ sudo ssh -l root <server_ip_address>
```

Insert your root password, created in step 4.v) when the VPS was ordered. A similar output on the terminal should then appear.


```
C:\Users\Tomas>ssh -l root 193.70.244.102
root@193:~#
Welcome to Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS (GNU/Linux 5.15.0-25-generic x86_64)

 * Documentation:  https://help.ubuntu.com
 * Management:    https://landscape.canonical.com
 * Support:       https://ubuntu.com/advantage

CONTABO
Welcome!
This server is hosted by Contabo. If you have any questions or need help,
please don't hesitate to contact us at support@contabo.com.
Last login: 2023-07-11 14:59:45
root@vml1459450:~#
```

Success! You have now accessed the cloud server of the STToolkit via SSH. You can now proceed to the [Server Hardening](#) section.

6.2. Cloud Server Hardening

These steps aim to customize and give more protection and security to the Cloud Server.

Please follow the steps below in the correct order.

1) Create a new *sttoolkit* user

- i) Log into your Cloud Server via SSH:

```
$ ssh root@<server-ip-address>
```

- ii) Create a new *sttoolkit* user:

```
$ adduser sttoolkit
```

- iii) Then, add *sttoolkit* user to sudo group (Super User):

```
$ usermod -aG sudo sttoolkit
```

- iv) Log into the Cloud Server via SSH with the new user:

```
$ ssh sttoolkit@<server-ip-address>
```

- v) Confirm that you can update the server with the new user:

```
$ sudo apt update && sudo apt upgrade
```

- vi) Restart the server:

```
$ sudo shutdown -r now
```

2) Disable root user login

After creating the new *sttoolkit* user, the initial root user is no longer needed. Therefore, we can disable its login.

- i) Login and open the SSH configuration file using the Nano editor. (Guide of how to use the Nano editor [here](#).)

```
$ sudo nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config
```

- ii) Look for the `PermitRootLogin` line, uncomment it (remove the `#`) and set the value to "no".

```
PermitRootLogin no
```

- iii) To apply the new settings, restart SSH service:

```
$ sudo service ssh restart
```

3) Set Up SSH Keys only login

The most secure way to connect to the server is by using SSH keys only, and not using account passwords. Therefore, we can set up logins only using SSH keypairs, and disable the username/password authentication method.

- i) Create a .ssh directory on the Cloud Server:

```
$ mkdir ~/.ssh
```

- ii) Create a new SSH keypair on the client machine (usually your personal computer):

Windows:

Open a new PowerShell window by clicking on the 'Windows' key and type 'Windows PowerShell'.

On the PowerShell, generate a new SSH keypair with the ssh-keygen command.

```
$ ssh-keygen
```

Press Enter for all parameters.

MacOS:

On a terminal window, create a new SSH keypair using the ssh-keygen command

```
$ ssh-keygen
```

Press Enter for all parameters.

- iii) Copy the SSH public key to the Cloud Server:

Windows:

On the PowerShell window, copy the *id_rsa.pub* public key to the Cloud Server using the command below. Replace the <server_ip_address> with the IP address of the Cloud Server.

```
type $env:USERPROFILE\.ssh\id_rsa.pub | ssh \
sttoolkit@<server_ip_address> "cat >> .ssh/authorized_keys"
```

MacOS:

Copy your public key to the Cloud Server using the command below. Replace the <server_ip_address> with the IP address of the Cloud Server.

```
$ ssh-copy-id sttoolkit@<server-ip-address>
```

iv) Log into the remote host without providing the remote account's password:

```
$ ssh sttoolkit@<server-ip-address>
```

If successful, notice that your client machine logged in to the Cloud Server without using any password. We can now remove the login via SSH using account passwords.

Note: Only proceed with the following steps if you successfully accomplished the previous step, otherwise you can lose connection to the Cloud Server. If you did not accomplish the previous steps, you can stick with the username/password authentication method and proceed with step 4) of this manual.

v) Open up the SSH daemon's configuration file:

```
$ sudo nano /etc/ssh/sshd_config
```

vi) Disable your ability to log in via SSH using account passwords by looking for the PasswordAuthentication line, uncomment it (remove the #) and set the value to no:

```
PasswordAuthentication no
```

At this point, the only way to log in to the Cloud Server is using SSH keys. Only the client machines that setup a SSH keypair with the Cloud server (described in steps ii) and iii)) will be able to connect to the Cloud Server. **You can repeat the steps ii), iii) and iv) for each client machine you wish to connect to the Cloud Server.**

4) Set local date (optional)

Run the dpkg-reconfigure command to set the datetime according to your timezone.

```
$ sudo dpkg-reconfigure tzdata
```

5) Setup Automatic Updates

i) Install the unattended-upgrades package and activate it.

```
$ sudo apt install unattended-upgrades
```

ii) Enable automatic updates in order to generate the files you need to customize:

```
$ sudo dpkg-reconfigure --priority=low unattended-upgrades
```

iii) Enable auto reboot and notifications:

```
$ sudo apt install update-notifier-common
```

iv) Open the 50unattended-upgrades file with Vim to configure what you need to be updated.

```
$ sudo nano /etc/apt/apt.conf.d/50unattended-upgrades
```

Enable reboots after updating. Locate the line below and uncomment it, then update them accordingly.

```
Unattended-Upgrade::Automatic-Reboot "true";
```

You can set a specific time for the reboot based on the 24hour clock system. We recommend the reboot for the early morning, such as 4 AM:

```
Unattended-Upgrade::Automatic-Reboot-Time "04:00"
```

6) Change Server Hostname

i) Set your Ubuntu server hostname as follows.

```
$ sudo hostnamectl set-hostname crowdingServer
```

ii) Edit the hosts file – /etc/hosts

```
$ sudo nano /etc/hosts
```

Change the old name to ‘crowdingServer’ in the hosts file.

The file should look as follows:

```
127.0.0.1    localhost
127.0.1.1    crowdingServer crowdingServer
# The following lines are desirable for IPv6 capable hosts
::1        localhost ip6-localhost ip6-loopback
ff02::1    ip6-allnodes
ff02::2    ip6-allrouters
192.168.1.1    crowdingServer crowdingServer
```

iii) Restart the server:

```
$ sudo shutdown -r now
```

7) Enable Firewall

i) Allow SSH connections so that you can log into your server next time by typing:

```
$ sudo ufw allow OpenSSH
```

ii) Run the following command in order to allow Webmin through the firewall:

```
$ sudo ufw allow 10000
```

iii) Enable the HTTP port:

```
$ sudo ufw allow 80
```

iv) Enable the InfluxDB port:

```
$ sudo ufw allow 8086
```

v) Enable the Grafana port:

```
$ sudo ufw allow 3000
```

vi) Enable the firewall:

```
$ sudo ufw enable
```

vii) You can see what network connections are allowed by typing:

```
$ sudo ufw status
```

The firewall is now active and enabled on the Cloud Server, and will only allow network traffic from the applications needed for the STToolkit.

The Cloud Server is now more secure and protected. It is now necessary to install and configure the software components for crowd monitoring, namely:

- The InfluxDB database, responsible for the data ingestion of all crowding sensors;

- The Grafana data visualization platform that will render the collected information from sensors to end users.

6.3. InfluxDB database Installation and Configuration

6.3.1. InfluxDB database installation

The steps given below describe the installation of the InfluxDB database on the Cloud Server.

1) Start with a system update

```
$ sudo apt-get update
```

2) Import the InfluxDB GPG key

```
$ wget -q https://repos.influxdata.com/influxdata-archive_compat.key
```

3) Add APT repository

```
$ echo  
'393e8779c89ac8d958f81f942f9ad7fb82a25e133faddaf92e15b16e6ac9ce4c \  
influxdata-archive_compat.key' | sha256sum -c && cat \  
influxdata-archive_compat.key | gpg --dearmor | sudo tee \  
/etc/apt/trusted.gpg.d/influxdata-archive_compat.gpg > /dev/null
```

```
$ echo 'deb  
[signed-by=/etc/apt/trusted.gpg.d/influxdata-archive_compat.gpg] \  
https://repos.influxdata.com/debian stable main' | sudo tee \  
/etc/apt/sources.list.d/influxdata.list
```

4) Update the system

```
$ sudo apt-get update
```

5) Install InfluxDB on the server

```
$ sudo apt-get install influxdb2
```

6) Start and Enable the InfluxDB service

```
$ sudo systemctl start influxdb
```

```
$ sudo systemctl enable influxdb
```

7) Check the status of the InfluxDB service

```
$ sudo systemctl status influxdb
```

An output similar to the following should appear. If the status of the InfluxDB service appears as 'active (running)', the InfluxDB service is available and running on the Cloud Server.

```
root@vmi1459450:~# sudo systemctl status influxdb
● influxdb.service - InfluxDB is an open-source, distributed, time series database
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/influxdb.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Tue 2023-09-19 20:30:46 CEST; 5h 26min ago
     Docs: https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb/
    Main PID: 4598 (influxd)
      Tasks: 11 (limit: 9457)
     Memory: 52.8M
        CPU: 31.994s
    CGroup: /system.slice/influxdb.service
            └─4598 /usr/bin/influxd

Sep 19 23:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T21:30:46.839061Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 19 23:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T21:30:46.841931Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 00:00:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T22:00:46.844342Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 00:00:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T22:00:46.851257Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 00:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T22:30:46.843526Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 00:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T22:30:46.848431Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 01:00:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T23:00:46.948204Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 01:00:47 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T23:00:46.962993Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 01:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T23:30:46.845342Z lvl=info msg="
Sep 20 01:30:46 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net influxd-systemd-start.sh[4598]: ts=2023-09-19T23:30:46.854114Z lvl=info msg="
```

The InfluxDB database is now installed in the Cloud Server. It is now needed to configure and setup this database.

6.3.2. InfluxDB database configuration

The configuration of the InfluxDB database can be done in just a few simple steps using the InfluxDB User Interface (UI).

Let's open the InfluxDB UI.

- 1) Open a browser and type: **http://<server_ip_address>:8086**
- 2) A window similar to the following should appear on your browser. This is how you can access the InfluxDB database. Click on '**Get Started**'.
- 3) An initial user setup is required.

Insert the following fields:

- Username: **crowdingSTToolkit**
- Password: (as desired by you)
- Initial Organization Name: **InfluxDBCrowding**
- Initial Bucket Name: **DetectionsDB**

Note: Please make sure that you correctly insert these fields, without spaces. These will be the parameters that the multiple crowding sensors will need to also set for

updating information to this InfluxDB database, as well the parameters for establishing a Grafana connection, as further described in [Grafana Configuration](#).

This will be the initial configuration for the user, organization, and bucket. No additional users, organizations, or buckets will be further needed to be created for the STToolkit.

Click on 'Continue'.

- 4) The initial user setup was completed, and an authorization token with superuser privileges appears. This superuser token enables the creation of users, orgs, buckets, etc.

Note: Please make sure you copy and save this superuser token, as you won't be able to generate it and see it again!

Click on 'Configure Later', as no other configurations are required.

- 5) After this, the main menu of the InfluxDB UI appears. Here you can manage the InfluxDB database, such as manage organizations, buckets, and authorization tokens.

- 6) Get familiar with the InfluxDB Buckets:

On the left side bar, click on 'Buckets'. This will direct you to the buckets that you have in the InfluxDB database, namely, the initial 'DetectionsDB' bucket created in the initial setup.

- 7) Get familiar with the InfluxDB API Tokens:

On the left side bar, click on 'API Tokens'. This will direct you to the API Tokens that you have created in the InfluxDB database. The superuser token appears, here you can see its permissions, although you cannot obtain it again.

Let's create another API token that will be used for the sensors to upload the crowding information to this InfluxDB database. (It is not recommended to use the superuser token for that purpose).

8) Create a new API Token.

On the 'API Tokens' tab, click on 'Generate API Token' > 'Custom API Token'. On Resources, click on 'Buckets', and only mark the 'read' and 'write' options for the 'DetectionsDB' bucket. Then, click on 'Generate'.

You have successfully created a new API Token. **Please make sure you copy and save this token, as you won't be able to see it again!**

You can also change the name of the new API Token as you wish.

Everything is now set for the InfluxDB database. You can now log out if you want.

Note: From now on, for accessing the InfluxDB database from your browser, you only have to repeat the step 1), and insert the user credentials created for the InfluxDB in the initial setup on step 3):

- Username: crowdingSTToolkit
- Password: (as chosen by you in the initial setup in step 3))

6.4. Grafana Installation and Configuration

6.4.1. Grafana Installation

Complete the following steps to install the Grafana data visualization platform in the Cloud Server.

i) Install the prerequisite packages:

```
$ sudo apt-get install -y apt-transport-https \
software-properties-common wget
```

ii) Import the GPG key:

```
$ sudo mkdir -p /etc/apt/keyrings/
```

```
$ wget -q -O - https://apt.grafana.com/gpg.key | gpg --dearmor | \
sudo tee /etc/apt/keyrings/grafana.gpg > /dev/null
```

iii) Add a repository for stable releases:

```
$ echo "deb [signed-by=/etc/apt/keyrings/grafana.gpg] \
https://apt.grafana.com stable main" | sudo tee -a \
/etc/apt/sources.list.d/grafana.list
```

iv) Update the list of available packages:

```
$ sudo apt-get update
```

v) Install Grafana:

```
$ sudo apt-get install grafana
```

vi) Start the Grafana service:

```
$ sudo systemctl start grafana-server
```

vii) Check if the Grafana service is running:

```
$ sudo systemctl status grafana-server
```

An output similar to the following should appear. If the status of the InfluxDB service appears as 'active (running)', the InfluxDB service is available and running on the Cloud Server.

```
root@vmi1459450:~# sudo systemctl status grafana-server
● grafana-server.service - Grafana instance
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/grafana-server.service; disabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: active (running) since Tue 2023-09-19 21:12:20 CEST; 23h ago
     Docs: http://docs.grafana.org
    Main PID: 6354 (grafana)
      Tasks: 14 (limit: 9457)
     Memory: 76.8M
        CPU: 6min 46.051s
    CGroup: /system.slice/grafana-server.service
           └─6354 /usr/share/grafana/bin/grafana server --config=/etc/grafana/grafana.ini --pidfile=/run/grafana/grafa

Sep 20 19:52:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=cleanup t=2023-09-20T19:52:30.673135077+02:00 level=i
Sep 20 19:52:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=plugins.update.checker t=2023-09-20T19:52:30.77494757
Sep 20 19:52:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=grafana.update.checker t=2023-09-20T19:52:30.81232264
Sep 20 20:02:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=cleanup t=2023-09-20T20:02:30.660263147+02:00 level=i
Sep 20 20:02:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=plugins.update.checker t=2023-09-20T20:02:30.7764423+
Sep 20 20:02:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=grafana.update.checker t=2023-09-20T20:02:30.81391427
Sep 20 20:12:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=cleanup t=2023-09-20T20:12:30.676171459+02:00 level=i
Sep 20 20:12:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=grafana.update.checker t=2023-09-20T20:12:30.81579702
Sep 20 20:12:30 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=plugins.update.checker t=2023-09-20T20:12:30.83484990
Sep 20 20:13:09 vmi1459450.contaboserver.net grafana[6354]: logger=infra.usagestats t=2023-09-20T20:13:09.025878168+02:0
```

6.4.2. Grafana Configuration

After the installation of Grafana, it is now necessary to configure this data visualization platform for the STToolkit.

1) Sign in to Grafana

- i) Open a browser and type the following URL: **http://<server_ip_address>:3000**

The Grafana login panel should appear.

- ii) On the signin page, enter **admin** for username and password.
- iii) Click **Sign In**.

If successful, you will see a prompt to change the password.

- iv) Click **OK** on the prompt and change your password.

Note: We strongly recommend that you change the default administrator password.

After this, you will be prompted to the Grafana Main Menu panel.

2) Configure the InfluxDB data source

- i) Click Connections in the left-side menu.

- ii) Click **Data source > Add new data source**.
- iii) Enter **InfluxDB** in the search bar.
- iv) Select **InfluxDB**.

The **Settings** tab of the data source is displayed.

It is now necessary to configure this data source to the InfluxDB database.

It will be through this connection that Grafana will be able to query, and render the crowding information stored in the InfluxDB database.

- v) Set the data source configuration as follows:
 - a. **Name:** (as desired by you) (**Suggestion:** InfluxDB Data Source)
 - b. **Query Language:** Flux
 - c. **HTTP:**
 - URL: http://<server_ip_address>:8086
 - Allowed cookies: (Leave blank)
 - Timeout: (Leave blank)
 - d. **Auth:** Basic auth
 - e. **Basic Auth Details:**
 - User: crowdingSTToolkit
 - Password: <InfluxDB_user_password>
 - f. **InfluxDB Details:**
 - Organization: InfluxDBCrowding
 - Token: (Insert the Authorization token created in the step 8) of the [InfluxDB database configuration](#))
 - Default Bucket: DetectionsDB
 - Min time interval: 10s
 - Max series: 1000
- vi) Click **Save & test**.

If the output “datasource is working. 1 bucket found” shows, this means that you have correctly configured the InfluxDB data source.

3) Import the STToolkit Crowding monitoring dashboard:

The last step regards the pre-configured Grafana dashboard of the STToolkit. This dashboard will allow you (and also the end users) to monitor crowding at the several locations where the sensors are deployed.

- i) First, download the STToolkit Crowding dashboard .json file to your personal computer from the [RESETTING GitHub repository](#).
- ii) Then, on Grafana, click on the Grafana icon on the top left corner to go to **Home**.
- iii) On the top right corner, select the > **Import dashboard**.

- iv) Click **Upload dashboard JSON file**.
- v) Select the .json file of the downloaded STToolkit Crowding dashboard.

The dashboard options are already set to this dashboard.

You only need to select the InfluxDB data source previously created.

A screenshot of the 'Import dashboard' form in Grafana. The form has a dark background and white text. At the top, it says 'Import dashboard' and 'Import dashboard from file or Grafana.com'. Below this is the 'Options' section. There are three input fields: 'Name' with the value 'STToolkit Crowding Dashboard', 'Folder' with a dropdown menu showing 'General', and 'Unique identifier (UID)' with the value 'Yrh2rpe4z34' and a 'Change uid' button. Below these is a section for 'InfluxDB - InfluxDbCrowding' with a dropdown menu showing 'InfluxDB Data Source'. At the bottom, there are two buttons: 'Import' and 'Cancel'.

vi) Click **Import**.

The dashboard is now imported on Grafana and is shown in the image below.

The dashboard does not show any data because any sensor was not installed and configured yet. Once you install and configure each sensor, the data will automatically appear on this dashboard.

The explanation of how to use and edit this dashboard is further explained in the [Operation Manual](#).

You have now successfully installed and configured the STToolit's Cloud Server. You can now proceed with the installation and configuration of the STToolkit's Crowd Sensors described in the [Crowd Sensor Installation Manual](#).

6.5. References

For more information about the technologies used in the STToolkit's Cloud Server, check the documentation pages in the following links:

- Contabo documentation: <https://docs.contabo.com/>
- InfluxDB OSS documentation: <https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb/v2/>
- Grafana documentation: <https://grafana.com/docs/grafana/latest/>

7. Crowd Sensor Installation Manual

This manual includes the step-by-step detailed tutorial for the installation and configuration of the STToolkit's crowd sensors, and the software that lives on them, after installing and configuring the cloud server.

7.1. Sensor Equipment Acquisition

First, it is necessary to acquire the equipment for mounting each sensor. The several hardware options for each sensor component are described on the Bill of Materials in the Deliverable. This guide presents the several options and the recommended option for each component. Make sure that you have at least one of this hardware options for mounting the sensor:

- **Single Computer Board (SBC):**
 - Raspberry Pi 4 4 GB RAM (recommended)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 1 GB RAM

- **Micro-SD card:**
 - 16 GB (minimum)
 - 32 GB (recommended)
 - > 64 GB (optimum)

- **Wi-Fi card:**
 - Alfa Network AWUS036ACH
 - Alfa Network AWUS036AC (recommended)

- **Raspberry Pi Power Supply:**
 - Raspberry Pi 4 USB-C Power Supply (recommended)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 Micro-USB Power Supply

- **USB Extension cable (Male to Female) with at least 10 cm length**

- **Sensor Case:**
 - Larger version with no exposed antennas (recommended)
 - Smaller version with exposed antennas

The sensor cases can be manufactured using 3D printing or a laser cutting machine. The files used to build them are available in the [RESETTING GitHub repository](#), along with some images of both case versions. These cases can be fabricated at a lab with a 3D printer or a laser-cutting machine. For instance, your sensor cases can be fabricated at [Vitruvius Fablab](#), an architecture lab at Iscte, which you can contact to manufacture these cases.

7.2. Flashing OS image on SD card

This section describes the steps for flashing the SD card with the software required for the sensor. Make sure that you have the following requisites.

Requirements:

- Windows computer with at least 15 GB free disk space and with SD card reader.
- Empty micro-SD card with at least 16 GB of space.

The steps for flashing the SD card are the following:

- 1) Download the “STToolkitCrowdSensorImage.img” compressed image file from the [FileSender FCCN platform](#). This file contains the setup image with all the installed software for the crowd sensor.
- 2) Extract the software image file.
- 3) Connect the empty micro-SD card to your personal computer.
- 4) Flash the SD card:
 - i) Download the [BalenaEtcher](#) software.
 - ii) Open the BalenaEtcher application on your computer.

- iii) Select the downloaded image file by clicking on “Flash from file”.

iv) Select the micro-SD card by clicking on “Select target”. (If not already selected by the application).

v) Flash the OS image by clicking on “Flash”.

- vi) The software will flash the OS image to the SD card. If the message “Insert a disk in SDXC” or similar appears just ignore and close the window. This process might take a few minutes so be patient and wait until it finishes.

- vii) If “Flash complete” appears on the application, the OS image was successfully flashed onto the SD card.

The OS image is now flashed on the SD card and the sensor is now ready to be configured.

7.3. Sensor Configuration

After flashing the OS image on the SD card, the next steps regard the configuration of the sensor.

7.3.1. Preliminary configurations

These steps require graphical interaction and so it is required to connect the Raspberry Pi to a monitor.

Requirements:

- Raspberry Pi;
- Raspberry Pi Power Supply;
- Micro SD-card (with the flashed OS image);
- Monitor, wired keyboard, and wired mouse;
- Micro-HDMI adapter to connect to the Raspberry Pi;
- Wi-Fi card for Wi-Fi detection of devices (see [Sensor Equipment Acquisition](#)).

The steps are the following:

- 1) Insert the SD card with the flashed OS image on the Raspberry Pi.
- 2) Connect the Wi-Fi card to the Raspberry Pi through the USB port.

Note: Connect the Wi-Fi card on the 2.0 USB ports (the ones not blue-coloured).

- 3) Connect the wired keyboard and wired mouse to two USB ports of the Raspberry Pi.
- 4) Connect the Raspberry Pi to the monitor.
- 5) Power the Raspberry Pi.

After a few seconds, a loading screen should appear asking for username and password credentials.

- 6) Insert the default user credentials:
 - **username:** kali
 - **password:** kali

A desktop should appear. You can now do the preliminary configurations of the sensor.

A. Change user password (optional)

This step may be important for security reasons, as the default password for accessing the sensor is very weak.

- 1) Open a new terminal window by pressing 'CTR + ALT + T'.
- 2) Enter the following command to change the kali user password.

```
$ sudo passwd
```

- 3) Enter the original password 'kali' and replace it with the new password.

This will be the new password required for accessing the sensor.

- 4) Close the terminal window.

B. Change local time zone (optional)

For convenience, you may want to set the sensor date and time according to the local time zone. For this, you need to find out the long name of the time zone you want to use. The time zone naming convention usually uses a "Region/City" format.

- 1) Open a new terminal window by pressing 'CTR + ALT + T'.
- 2) To view all available time zones, use the `timedatectl` command:

```
$ timedatectl list-timezones
```

- 3) Once you identify which time zone is accurate to your location, run the following command:

```
$ sudo timedatectl set-timezone <your_time_zone>
```

- 4) For example, to change the system's timezone to `America/New_York` you would type:

```
$ sudo timedatectl set-timezone America/New_York
```

- 5) To verify the change, invoke the `timedatectl` command:

```
$ timedatectl
```

You have now successfully changed the system's time zone to your location.

- 6) Close the terminal window.

C. Extending available disk space

For extending the available disk space to the total space of the SD card do the following steps:

- 1) Open a new terminal window by pressing 'CTR + ALT + T'.
- 2) Open GParted application using sudo privileges.

```
$ sudo gparted
```

- 3) When the GParted application opens, it should appear a window similar to the following:

Here notice a few things:

- There are two partitions: BOOT and ROOTFS.
- There is a huge part of the disk with unallocated space. This is the remaining part of the SD card that is necessary to extend to the disk.

- 4) For extending the disk space to the total available space of the SD card, select the ROOTFS partition. Then click on 'Resize/Move the selected partition'.

5) A window similar to the following should pop up:

6) Drag the right bar to the right as much as possible.

7) Press the 'Resize' button. You will return to the GParted window. This time it will look similar to the following.

- 8) Finally, commit the changes by clicking on 'Apply All Operations'. Confirm the operation by clicking on 'Apply' in the pop up window. It will perform the extension so it can take a minute or two, but most of the time it finishes quickly.

- 9) If the operation succeeds, it should produce a similar output to the following. Afterwards you can close GParted.

Now the OS image is using the full space of the SD card.

D. Connect to a Wi-Fi network graphically

A Wi-Fi connection is necessary for the operation of the sensor. It is required for the data upload, and also for the remote access to the sensor, allowing to perform over-the-air updates as well as changing configuration parameters as desired by the STToolkit operator.

The configuration of a Wi-Fi connection can be performed graphically in just a few steps.

IMPORTANT NOTES:

- The configuration of the Wi-Fi connection requires having the Wi-Fi card connected to the Raspberry Pi. **If that is not the case, connect the Wi-Fi card to the Raspberry Pi on the USB 2.0 ports and reboot the sensor.** This is very important because the wireless interfaces have an order that needs to be followed, otherwise the sensor will not run correctly.
- It is recommended to configure the Wi-Fi connection where the sensor will be deployed, i.e., where the Wi-Fi network coverage that the sensor will connect to is available. If that is not possible go to the [Configure Wi-Fi connection not on deployment location](#) section.

Configure Wi-Fi connection on deployment location

Having the Wi-Fi card connected to the Raspberry Pi and being on the network coverage provided by the Wi-Fi network that the sensor will connect to, the Wi-Fi connection can be configured.

- 1) On the Desktop, click on the network icon displayed as .
- 2) Left-click on the network icon. It will show the available Wi-Fi networks on each Wi-Fi card. On the networks available for the 'Broadcom BCM 43438' board, select the Wi-Fi network to connect to.

- 3) Select the correct Wi-Fi adapter and insert the password of the Wi-Fi network (if required).

At this point you should have established the connection to the Wi-Fi network.

- 4) To strict the Wi-Fi connection to the Wi-Fi card of the Raspberry Pi, open the '**Advanced Network Configuration**' by searching it on the **Start menu**. You should see the network configuration that you have just created. (If you see other network connections, delete them by clicking on the "-" button.)

- 5) Select the created network connection and edit it by clicking on the wheel button.
- 6) Click on the 'Device', and select one of the following options according to the Raspberry Pi model of the sensor:
 - Raspberry Pi 4 □ wlan1 (DC:A6:32:XX:XX:XX)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 □ wlan0 (DC:A6:32:XX:XX:XX)

The image below shows an example using a Raspberry Pi 4, where you should select 'wlan1 (DC:A6:32:XX:XX:XX)'.

7) Afterwards, you can close the Advanced Network Configuration window.

Configure Wi-Fi connection not on deployment location

Having the Wi-Fi card connected to the Raspberry Pi and not being on the network coverage provided by the Wi-Fi network that the sensor will connect to, the Wi-Fi connection can also be configured.

- 8) Open the '**Advanced Network Configuration**' by searching it on the **Start menu**.
- 1) Create a new network connection by clicking on the "+" icon.
- 2) Select 'Hardware' > 'Wi-Fi', and then 'Create...'.
 - 3) On the 'Wi-Fi' section, insert the SSID of the Wi-Fi network, and on the 'Device' select one of the following options according to the Raspberry Pi model of the sensor:
 - Raspberry Pi 4 □ wlan1 (DC:A6:32:XX:XX:XX)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 □ wlan0 (DC:A6:32:XX:XX:XX)
 - 4) In the 'Wi-Fi Security' section, insert the Security required for the Wi-Fi network. The most usual are the 'WPA & WPA2 Personal' or 'WPA & WPA2 Enterprise' options.
 - 5) Afterwards, you can close the Advanced Network Configuration window.

E. Change the `dataRetentionManager.py` script

It is necessary to change the operation of the `dataRetentionManager.py` script. It is a minimal, but crucial change to the script correctly delete old and necessary data from the sensor local database.

- 1) Go to the Desktop.
- 2) Locate the `dataRetentionManager.py` python script. Right-click and then select "Open With 'Mousepad'".
- 3) A new window pops up with the script code, as shown below.

```

1 import sqlite3
2 import datetime as dt
3 import pytz
4 import sys
5
6 if(len(sys.argv) < 2 ):
7     print("Argument not provided. Please specify an argument with the 'sliding window' time in minutes.")
8     exit(0)
9
10 if(len(sys.argv) > 2 ):
11     print("Too many arguments required. Please specifit only one argument with the 'sliding window time', in minutes.")
12     exit(0)
13
14 if not sys.argv[1].isdigit():
15     print("The sliding window is not an integer. Please set the 'sliding window' time, in minutes, as an integer.")
16     exit(0)
17 else:
18     dataAtual = dt.datetime.now(pytz.utc).replace(tzinfo=None)
19     dataAnalizar= dataAtual - dt.timedelta(minutes=int(sys.argv[1]))
20
21
22     #Delele old and unnecessary data from the local database
23
24     connwifi = sqlite3.connect('/home/kali/Desktop/DB/DeviceRecords.db', timeout=30)
25     cwifi = connwifi.cursor()
26     cwifi.execute("""DELETE FROM Data_Packets WHERE ((First_Record > ? and First_Record <= ?) or (Last_Time_Found > ? and Last_Time_Found <= ?))""", (dataAnalizar, dataAtual,
27 dataAnalizar, dataAtual))
28     connwifi.commit()
29     cwifi.execute("""DELETE FROM Probe_Requests WHERE ((First_Record > ? and First_Record <= ?) or (Last_Time_Found > ? and Last_Time_Found <= ?))""", (dataAnalizar,
30 dataAtual, dataAnalizar, dataAtual))
31     connwifi.commit()
32     cwifi.close()

```

4) On the lines 26 and 28 of the code, add the word “NOT” after the word “WHERE”, as shown in the image below.

```

21
22     #Delele old and unnecessary data from the local database
23
24     connwifi = sqlite3.connect('/home/kali/Desktop/DB/DeviceRecords.db', timeout=30)
25     cwifi = connwifi.cursor()
26     cwifi.execute("""DELETE FROM Data_Packets WHERE NOT ((First_Record > ? and First_Record <= ?) or (Last_Time_Found >
27 dataAtual, dataAnalizar, dataAtual))
28     connwifi.commit()
29     cwifi.execute("""DELETE FROM Probe_Requests WHERE NOT ((First_Record > ? and First_Record <= ?) or (Last_Time_Found
30 dataAtual, dataAnalizar, dataAtual))
31     connwifi.commit()
32     cwifi.close()
33

```

5) Save the script on File > Save or by clicking ‘CTR + S’.

6) Close the window.

The *dataRetentionManager.py* script is now with the correct configuration for its execution.

7.3.2. Cloud Server connectivity configuration

After doing all the preliminary configurations. It is now time to configure the cloud server connectivity. For this, we will make the use of the custom-made scripts developed for the sensor.

IMPORTANT NOTE:

- These steps assume that the Cloud Server has already been installed and configured, including the InfluxDB database. If not so, please go back to the [Cloud Server Installation](#) and then proceed to this section.
- We also recommend proceeding with these steps by remotely accessing the Raspberry Pi, and not using the graphical connection. You can use the [Advanced IP Scanner](#) tool to discover the IP address of the Raspberry Pi to remotely connect to.

- 1) Open a terminal window by clicking 'CTR + ALT + T'.
- 2) Go to the Desktop directory.

```
$ cd /home/kali/Desktop
```

The sensor needs an upload configuration to upload the crowding data to the Cloud Server. This configuration can be configured using the `influxDBUploadConfig.py` python script.

- 3) Run the `influxDBUploadConfig.py` python script.

```
$ python3 influxDBUploadConfig.py
```

The script will ask you to insert some parameters. These parameters are necessary to configure the data upload to the InfluxDB database already created when the Cloud Server was installed.

The Cloud Server IP address and the Authorization Token will differ for you. The InfluxDB Organization and Bucket names are the default names already created when installing the InfluxDB database on the Cloud Server.

- i) Insert the Cloud Server IP address.
 - ii) Insert the default InfluxDB Organization Name '**InfluxDBCrowding**'. This is the default name of the default InfluxDB Organization already created in the Cloud Server.
 - iii) Insert the default InfluxDB Bucket Name '**CrowdingDB**'. This is the default name of the default InfluxDB Bucket already created in the Cloud Server.
 - iv) Insert the Authorization Token created during the installation of the Cloud Server.
 - v) Finally, if the message 'Done! The new InfluxDB upload configuration was correctly saved.', you have successfully created the upload configuration to the Cloud Server.
- 4) Verify the current upload configuration by running the `checkInfluxDBConfig.py` python script.

```
$ python3 checkInfluxDBConfig.py
```

The output should be something similar to this:

```
(kali@ kali-raspberry-pi) - [~/Desktop]
└─$ python3 checkInfluxDBConfig.py
The active InfluxDB Upload Configuration is:

Cloud Server IP Address: 192.120.31.23
InfluxDB Organization Name: InfluxDBCrowding
InfluxDB Bucket Name: DetectionsDB
InfluxDB Authorization Token: qxVvbfKPAJs0X0e_9jYo_gyF9Z4XGNsdUQVICJjQqZcteDNiPqpqGsu4Uf3L60HPd6YTGPSzqG0FAUt9eQctQ==
```

Sensor location configuration

At this stage it is required to set the sensor location where it will be deployed. For this, use the `sendSensorLocation.py` python script.

The sensor location can always be configured and altered by running this script. For instance, if you want to change the sensor's current location to another location, simply run this script again, making sure that you specify the correct sensor name.

1) Open a terminal window by clicking 'CTR + ALT + T'.

2) Go to the Desktop directory.

```
$ cd /home/kali/Desktop
```

3) Run the `sendSensorLocation.py` python script.

```
$ python3 sendSensorLocation.py
```

i) Insert the sensor name. We recommend that the name should be related to the deployment location of the sensor. E.g.: 'Main Entrance', 'Public Square'.

Note: Do not use spaces on the sensor name. Use the '_' character instead of spaces. E.g.: 'Main_Entrance', 'Public_Square'.

ii) Enter the latitude and longitude of the current deployment location of the sensor. You can use [Google Maps](#) for this purpose. Search for the location, then right-click on the location, and copy and paste the latitude and longitude coordinates.

Note: The latitude and longitude are inserted individually. First the latitude and then the longitude.

iii) Confirm the location to be set/altered for the sensor.

iv) An output similar to the following should appear.

```
(kali@ kali-raspberry-pi) [~/Desktop]
└─$ python3 sendSensorLocation.py
Welcome! This script allows to set/alter the sensor location where it is currently deployed.
IMPORTANT NOTE: If a sensor location was already sent with the same sensor name, the location
of that sensor will be altered to this new location.

Please enter the sensor name: Main\ Entrance
The sensor name to set/alter the location is: Main\ Entrance

Please enter the latitude of the sensor: 38.74872
Please enter the longitude of the sensor: -9.15364

The latitude and longitude (38.74872, -9.15364) will be set for the 'Main\ Entrance'. Are you sure? (Yes/No) Yes

HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
X-Influxdb-Build: OSS
X-Influxdb-Version: v2.3.0+SNAPSHOT.090f681737
Date: Sat, 16 Sep 2023 13:21:51 GMT

Location for the 'Main\ Entrance' sensor sent to the cloud server.
```

If the 'HTTP/1.1 204 No Content' message appears on the output, the sensor location was successfully sent to the InfluxDB, meaning that the sensor location was received in the Cloud Server.

If you want to change the location of the sensor to another location, simply run this script again, making sure that you specify the same sensor name.

Tasks Automation configuration

The final steps regard the automation of the tasks of the sensor. This is mandatory for the automatization of the sensor.

The automation of the sensor tasks can be configured in the crontab file. This file contains several commands that are executed on predetermined time schedules.

- 1) Edit the crontab file by entering the following command.

```
$ crontab -u kali -e
```

This command will open your crontab file in the system's default text editor.

The final part of the file contains the several tasks that the sensor needs to perform, as shown below. The function of each task is identified with a comment above it.

```
# Insert your tasks to run automatically above:
#
#@reboot sudo service smb restart
# Start monitor mode on Wi-Fi network card
#@reboot sudo airmon-ng start wlan0
# Wi-Fi detection of devices
*/10 * * * * timeout -k 1 590s sudo airodump-ng --background 1 wlan0
*/10 * * * * sleep 595 && sudo pkill airodump-ng
# Periodic upload of crowding data to the Cloud Server
*/5 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/sendCrowdingData.py SensorTest Wifi 5 wlan1
# Periodic delete of outdated and unnecessary data from local database
#0 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/dataRetentionManager.py 30
# Weekly upload of OUI list
#0 0 * * 0 /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/macOUIupdater.py
# Daily reboot
#0 4 * * * sudo reboot
```

2) Uncomment all tasks in the crontab file.

For uncommenting all tasks, press the letter 'I' to 'Insert'. This will enter the file in 'Insert' mode to edit it.

Then, go to the last part of the file, where the commented tasks are, and uncomment them by simply removing the '#' character at the beginning of each task.

```
# Insert your tasks to run automatically above:
#
@reboot sudo service smbd restart
# Start monitor mode on Wi-Fi network card
@reboot sudo airmon-ng start wlan0
# Wi-Fi detection of devices
*/10 * * * * timeout -k 1 590s sudo airodump-ng --background 1 wlan0
*/10 * * * * sleep 595 && sudo pkill airodump-ng
# Periodic upload of crowding data to the Cloud Server
*/5 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/sendCrowdingData.py SensorTest Wifi 5 wlan1
# Periodic delete of outdated and unnecessary data from local database
0 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/dataRetentionManager.py 30
# Weekly upload of OUI list
0 0 * * 0 /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/macOUIUpdater.py
# Daily reboot
0 4 * * * sudo reboot
~
~
~
~
~
-- INSERT --
```

3) Configure the tasks

Now let's walk through all the sensor tasks required for the sensor operation.

The parameters that you can change for each task are highlighted in blue.

i) Start monitor mode on Wi-Fi network card

Task: `@reboot sudo airmon-ng start wlan0`

Configuration:

- wlan0 □ Change the interface according to the Raspberry Pi model
 - Raspberry Pi 4 □ wlan0 (do not change)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 □ wlan1

ii) Wi-Fi detection of devices

Task: `*/10 * * * * timeout -k 1 590s sudo airodump-ng background 1 wlan0`

Configuration:

- wlan0 □ Change the interface according to the Raspberry Pi model
 - Raspberry Pi 4 □ wlan0 (do not change)

- Raspberry Pi 3 □ wlan1

iii) Periodic upload of crowding data to the Cloud Server

Task: `* /5 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/sendCrowdingData.py`
SensorTest Wifi 5 wlan1

Configuration:

- SensorTest □ Specify to the name of the sensor (Default: SensorTest)
- wlan1 □ Change the interface according to the Raspberry Pi model
 - Raspberry Pi 4 □ wlan1 (do not change)
 - Raspberry Pi 3 □ wlan0

iv) Periodic delete of outdated and unnecessary data from local database

Task: `0 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/dataRetentionManager.py 30`

Configuration: do not change anything.

v) Weekly upload of the OUI list

Task: `0 * * * * /usr/bin/python3 /home/kali/Desktop/macOUIupdater.py`

Configuration: do not change anything.

vi) Daily reboot

Task: `0 4 * * * sudo reboot`

Configuration: do not change anything.

4) Save the crontab file by clicking 'ESC', followed by ':wq'. Then press Enter to save the file.

5) Confirm the changes by entering the command.

```
$ crontab -u kali -l
```

The output should be the crontab file with the alterations applied. If not, go back to step 1) and repeat the process.

The sensor is now configured and ready to be deployed. The final step regards mounting the hardware inside the sensor case.

7.4. Sensor Mounting

These steps regard the sensor mounting at the deployment location, after configuring the sensor.

The sensor mounting is also available as a video tutorial on the [RESETTING YouTube channel](#), which you can also use to mount the sensor.

Make sure that you have the following equipment:

- Raspberry Pi 3 or Raspberry Pi 4;
- Raspberry Pi Power Supply (according to the Raspberry Pi model);
- Micro-SD card (with OS image flashed and configured from the previous steps);
- Alfa Network AWUS036AC or Alfa Network AWUS036ACH;
- USB extension cable (Male to Female);
- Sensor case;
- Screwdriver.

Follow the steps below to mount the sensor.

- 1) With the help of a screwdriver, open the sensor case;
- 2) Attach the Wi-Fi card on the bottom of the case;
- 3) Connect the USB extension cable to the Wi-Fi card;
- 4) Insert the SD card into the Raspberry Pi;
- 5) Attach the Raspberry Pi to the plastic sheet of the sensor case;
- 6) Connect the Raspberry Pi to the Wi-Fi card using the USB extension cable;
- 7) Connect the Power Supply to the Raspberry Pi;
- 8) With the help of a screwdriver, close the sensor case.

Done! The sensor is now ready to be deployed.

Power the sensor by plugging it into an electrical socket.

8. Operation Manual

This manual includes guidance of how to use the several applications installed on the Cloud Server, namely the InfluxDB database and the Grafana data visualisation platform, and how to troubleshoot some circumstances that can occur during the STToolkit runtime. It assumes that the Cloud Server and also the sensors are already installed and configured for the current STToolkit.

8.1. Grafana

The Grafana is the data visualization platform of the STToolkit. It is on this platform that you can visualize the crowding data collected by the several sensors deployed at several locations.

8.1.1. Log in into Grafana

You can access Grafana by inserting `<your_server_ip_address:3000>` on your browser.

The default user credentials are **admin** for both username and password. However, we expect that you have already changed the admin password to another stronger password, as described in the installation manual.

The Grafana also saves the log in sessions, for users do not have to introduce your user credentials every time they access Grafana.

8.1.2. Admin user

The STToolkit has access to the admin user. This user has permissions to do everything on Grafana, such as creating new users, changing their passwords, creating new organizations, creating new dashboards and editing them, etc.

The admin user has access to the **Administration** section on Grafana. This section includes information for Grafana administrators, team administrators, and users performing administrative tasks.

For more information about this section, check this [link](#).

8.1.3. Create a new user

You can create a new user on **Administration > Users > New user**.

Insert the required fields and then you have a new user created.

Each user has roles and permissions associated. By default, the new users have a default 'Viewer' role, which means that users can only visualize the information on Grafana, and do not have editing permissions.

For more information about roles and permissions, check this [link](#).

Note: We recommend creating a new user, with only visualization permissions (Viewer). This new user will be used by the STToolkit end users to visualize the crowding information by providing the credentials of this new user.

8.1.4. Crowding data visualization

If you have correctly installed and configured Grafana on the dashboard, you have already installed the pre-configured STToolkit Crowding dashboard on Grafana to visualize the crowding data.

You can access this dashboard by clicking **Dashboards** in the toggle menu on the left side, and then on **STToolkit Crowding Dashboard**.

If you have installed and configured the crowd sensors correctly, the crowding measurements from sensors should automatically be rendered on the dashboard.

An example of how data is rendered on this dashboard is shown in the image below.

How to use the crowding dashboard

The dashboard is composed by three main panels:

- **System General Information** – This panel is a table that shows the general information of the STToolkit. It queries information within the last hour. This table has 4 columns:
 - **Last Location** - The last sensor location measurement sent by each crowd sensor;
 - **Last Record** – The last crowding measurement sent by each sensor;
 - **Sensor** - The name of the sensor;
 - **Detected devices** – The number of devices detected in the last crowding measurement sent by each sensor.
- **Crowding Comparison** – This panel is a graph that allows a temporal rendering of the crowding information. This graph shows the last crowding measurements from the sensors selected in the 'Sensors' button on the top left corner of the dashboard. It queries the crowding information within the selected time range selected on the top right corner. The time range can be selected to any start and end time as you wish. This graph allows you to visualize crowding tendencies along the passage of each day, compare crowding from sensors, and also to perceive highly-populated events.
- **Crowding Geodistribution** – This panel is a map that allows you to visualize the crowding geodistribution. It queries information within the last hour. With this map you can observe how the crowding is spatially distributed at the several locations where the sensors are currently deployed. It renders and matches both sensor locations and crowding measurements. Each heatmap circle represents the location where the sensors are deployed, and are accompanied by the number of detected devices of the last crowding measurement sent by each sensor.

This map allows a quick and easy interpretation of the crowding phenomena at the several target locations where the sensors are deployed, allowing to perceive crowding tendencies throughout the days with the temporal graph, and also to observe how the crowding is spatially distributed across the several locations.

As the Operator, you can edit this dashboard, add new panels, change their settings and configurations as you wish, although the dashboard already allows a good and quick interpretation of crowding with the default panels.

For more information about Grafana dashboards, check this [link](#).

For more information about Grafana panels and visualization, check this [link](#).

System General Information panel

There are no meaningful editions to perform on this panel.

You can order the table by a column by selecting it.

Crowding Comparison panel

This panel shows the crowding levels on the time range selected on the top right corner of the dashboard.

Choose the sensors which you want to visualize the crowding levels on the 'Sensor' button on the top left corner.

Note: If this panel shows an error when the dashboard is first loaded, just **unselect and select again a sensor on the 'Sensor' button.**

You can also change the name that is displayed for each sensor. To do this, you need to add an Override to the name of each sensor. To add an Override, click on the three dots icon and then on 'Edit' to edit the graph. In the right-hand menu, click on 'Overrides'. Click 'Add field override'. Select 'Fields with name'. Choose the sensor name you wish to change. Click 'Add override property', and select 'Standard options > Display name'. Enter the name of the sensor to be shown. Once you add the Override, the name of the sensor shown in the graph has changed to the name you chose in Override. You can change the name that is displayed for each sensor by adding a Override just like this to each sensor.

Crowding Geodistribution

Once you import the pre-configured dashboard, the 'Crowding Geodistribution' map comes with a very zoomed out initial view by default. The initial view configures how the map renders when the panel is first loaded. You can (and should) set the initial view of the map to an area closer to your sensors. For this, you need to edit this map.

To edit the 'Crowding Geodistribution' map, click on the three dots icon on the top right corner of the map, and select **Edit**.

Use your mouse to drag and the mouse wheel to zoom in and out until you find the correct initial view for the map. Then, click on 'Use current map settings' to set the initial view. Then, click on 'Apply' to apply the changes. Click on 'Save' on the top right corner to save the dashboard. Reload the dashboard. The initial view when the dashboard is loaded has now changed to the view that you specified.

For more information about this map, check the [Grafana geomap documentation](#).

You can also change the that is displayed for each sensor by adding an Override to each sensor name, as shown for the previous panel.

8.2. InfluxDB

The InfluxDB is the main database of the STToolkit and is responsible for the data ingestion and storing the collected data from all sensors.

8.2.1. Log in into InfluxDB

You can access InfluxDB by inserting `<your_server_ip_address:8086>` on your browser.

The user credentials are the ones created when the initial setup configuration of the InfluxDB database was created.

8.2.2. Manage InfluxDB database

You can manage organizations, buckets, and the authorization tokens using the InfluxDB UI.

To manage users, you need to use the InfluxDB CLI.

- You can add users by following this [link](#).
- You can change the user's password by following this [link](#).

For more information about InfluxDB, check the [InfluxDB documentation](#).

8.2.3. Sensor measurements visualization

In InfluxDB, you can also visualize the measurements sent by the sensors on the **Data Explorer** section. The **Data Explorer** allows you to build, execute, and visualize queries.

The image below shows how you can visualize the crowding level measurements sent to the *DetectionsDB* bucket.

Note that there is also an `ipAddress` field that is also sent in the crowding level measurements. This field is also sent to the Operator know which is the IP address that the sensor is using to upload the crowding data to the InfluxDB. Furthermore, this IP address is also sent so that the Operator can also know where to remotely access the sensor via SSH.

Therefore, the Operator should go into the InfluxDB Data Explorer section to know how to remotely access each sensor via SSH, as the IP address of the sensor is required.

8.3. Crowd Sensors

This section provides guidance on how to operate the STToolkit's crowd sensors.

The relevant files for the crowd sensor operation are all in the /Desktop directory. **Please do not change the location or the name of any file in this directory, as it can compromise its operation.**

In the Desktop of the sensor we have:

- *aircrack-ng-1.7* – This folder contains the aircrack-ng software for detecting Wi-Fi devices;
- DB – This directory contains the two sensor local databases:
 - *DeviceRecords.db* – This database contains the device's trace elements captured by the sensor;
 - *InfluxDBConfiguration.db* – This database contains the InfluxDB upload configuration with the required parameters for uploading the crowding data to the InfluxDB database.
- *macOUIUpdater.py* – A python script for updating the OUI list used to identify the manufacturer of the captured Wi-Fi frames.
- *dataRetentionManager.py* – A python script that deletes old and unnecessary data from the *DeviceRecords.db*, and only retaining useful information that is needed for device counting;
- *sendSensorLocation.py* – Python script to send the location where the sensor is deployed;
- *sendCrowdingData.py* – Python script to send the number of devices detected to InfluxDB. It is responsible for the periodic upload to InfluxDB of the crowding levels in the sensor's vicinity.
- *influxDBUploadConfig.py* – A python script to configure the InfluxDB upload configuration, with the required parameters to the sensor be able to send measurements to the InfluxDB;
- *checkInfluxDBConfig.py* – A python script to check the current InfluxDB upload configuration.

If the crowd sensor was correctly installed and configured, the operator does not have to perform anything, as the sensor will automatically operate on its own without any problem.

The operator should be able to change the configuration of the crowd sensor with ease if desired. The following sections show how to change the sensor configuration..

8.3.1. Remotely access the crowd sensor

To remotely access the crowd sensor, check the assigned IP address for the sensor on the InfluxDB Data Explorer, as shown in [this section](#).

Then, open a terminal window and type:

```
$ ssh -l kali <sensor_ip_address>
```

Enter the password for the kali user. The default password is also kali, but you could already have changed it during the sensor installation.

8.3.2. *Change the sensor location*

To change the sensor location, run the *sendSensorLocation.py* script. Make sure that you insert the same sensor name to change its location.

8.3.3. *Change the InfluxDB upload configuration*

To change the InfluxDB upload configuration, run the *influxDBUploadConfiguration.py* script. Insert the new parameters, namely, the Cloud Server IP address, InfluxDB organization, InfluxDB bucket, and the Authorization token.

8.3.4. *Test the Cloud Server connectivity*

To test the Cloud Server connectivity, run the *sendCrowdingData.py* script. If a 'HTTP 204' output appears, you have successfully sent a measurement to the InfluxDB database of the Cloud Server.

8.4. Troubleshooting

This section describes possible errors that can occur and how the operator should act upon them.

- **The 'Crowding Comparison' panel shows an 'undefined identifier' error.**
Unselect and then select the sensor in the 'Sensor' button.
- **There are no available sensors to select on the 'Sensor' button'.**
There are no crowding measurements sent by any sensor within the selected time range. Check if the time range is correctly selected to show the data on the panel.
- **Data shows on the 'Crowding Comparison' panel but not in the 'System General Information' and in the 'Crowding Geodistribution' panels.**

This can be due to two reasons:

1. All sensors did not send any measurement in the last hour. You can also verify this using the 'Crowding Comparison' map. It is possible that the sensors lost connectivity with the Cloud Server. Try to reboot them.
2. Check if the sensor location (*sendSensorLocation.py*) and the crowding level measurements (*sendCrowdingData.py*) have the same sensor name for the sensors.

If not, you need to remotely access them, and make sure that both measurements use the same sensor name.

- **Data shows on the 'System General Information' and on the 'Crowding geodistribution' but not in the 'Crowding Comparison' panel.**

There are no crowding measurements sent by any sensor within the selected time range. Check if the time range is correctly selected to show the data on the panel.

- **I have set the wrong name for the sensor.**

You have two options:

1. Override the sensor name in the dashboard panels. (most straightforward solution)
2. Remotely access the sensor and send a new sensor location measurement with the correct name of the sensor, and set the same new name to the crowding level measurements (more extensive solution, just as if a new sensor was installed)

- **I have set the wrong location for the sensor.**

Remotely access the sensor, and run the *sendSensorLocation.py* script again. Insert the sensor name you want to change the location and set it to the correct location. You can run this script and change the sensor location the times you want.

- **I have set the wrong InfluxDB upload configuration.**

Remotely access the sensor and run the *influxDBUploadConfig.py* script again. Make sure that you insert the correct server IP address, InfluxDB organization, InfluxDB bucket, and Authorization token.

- **The dashboard showed but now does not show any data on the three panels.**

This is very unlikely to happen. This means that any sensor sent any measurement at least within the last hour. Probably all sensors have lost connectivity to the Cloud Server. You can check when the last crowding measurement sent by each device was using the 'Crowding Comparison' panel and selecting different time ranges. Try to reboot the sensors, or unplug and plug it back to the electrical socket for a 'manual reboot'.

- **The dashboard never showed any data on the three panels.**

This is very unlikely to happen. Follow the steps below to troubleshoot this case:

1. Check if the InfluxDB upload configuration of the sensors is correctly configured by running the *checkInfluxDBConfig.py* script. If not, run the *influxDBUploadConfig.py* script and reconfigure it.
2. Test if the sensors can send information to the Cloud Server by manually running the *sendCrowdingData.py* script. If a 'HTTP 204' shows in the output, you have sent the measurement to the InfluxDB. If not, go to step 3.
3. Remotely connect to the Cloud Server, and check if the 8086 port is allowed in the firewall by running the *sudo ufw status* command. If not, add this port by running *sudo ufw allow 8086*. The same applies to the 3000 port. Run the *sudo ufw status* command to confirm the changes.

- **I have deconfigured the dashboard and do not know how to put it back.**

Delete the dashboard and import it again from the [GitHub repository](#).

- **The sensor is always sending measurements, but with '0' devices detected.**

The InfluxDB upload configuration is correctly set for the sensor, but the sensor is not performing the device counting. Make sure that you have uncommented the tasks for enabling the monitor mode on the Wi-Fi board and for performing the Wi-Fi detection of devices. If so, please make sure that you have the Wi-Fi board attached to the Raspberry Pi.

9. End User's Manual

This manual illustrates the experience of an STToolkit end user. It is targeted for the **STToolkit User role**. It includes guidelines for end users (e.g. tourism attraction managers), on how to use STToolkit's crowding information.

The end user can visualize the crowding information collected at the several spots where the STToolkit's crowd sensors are currently deployed. With this information, users can visualise the crowding levels in real-time at several hotspots, thus allowing them to make more informed decisions, for instance, to know where they should go if one of the locations is overcrowded.

9.1. Accessing the crowding information

The end user can visualize the crowding information by accessing the "STToolkit Crowding Dashboard" on Grafana, the data visualization platform of the STToolkit. This dashboard contains several panels that allow users to visualize the crowding data collected by the crowd sensors, deployed at several hotspots.

Users can visualize this dashboard either in a computer or in a mobile phone.

To access this dashboard, follow the steps below:

- 1) Open a web browser and type the following URL: **<server_ip_address>:3000**

The <server_ip_address> needs to be provided by the STToolkit Operator. This is the IP address of the STToolkit's Cloud Server, where the data visualization application is installed.

- 2) A log in screen appears. Insert the end user credentials provided by the STToolkit Operator.

Username: (provided by the STToolkit Operator)

Password: (provided by the STToolkit Operator)

You will be directed to the Grafana Main Menu.

- 3) On the left-side menu, click **Dashboards** and then on **STToolkit Crowding Dashboard**.

You have entered the "STToolkit Crowding Visualization" dashboard. You can then visualize the crowding data using this dashboard.

9.2. How to use the crowding dashboard

A snapshot of the crowding dashboard is shown below.

The 'System General Information' shows the last location measurement sent by each sensor, the last crowding level measurement sent by each sensor, the name of the sensor, and also the number of detected devices in the last measurement for each sensor.

The 'Crowding Comparison' graph shows the last crowding measurements sent by the sensors selected in the 'Sensor' button on the top left corner of the dashboard. The time range for this graph is selected on the top right corner of the dashboard.

The 'Crowding Geodistribution' map shows the geographical location of each sensor. The locations where the sensor are deployed are shown with a heatmap circle, along with the name of the sensor and also the number of detected devices in the last measurement sent by each sensor.

As the end user, you only have visualization permissions to this dashboard. Feel free to navigate through this dashboard and visualize the crowding data collected by the several sensors deployed at hotspot locations.

9.3. Sign out

You can sign out from Grafana by clicking on the user's icon, and then **Sign Out**.

